

Determination of Carbon-di-sulphide and Xanthates by Potassium periodate

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An accurate, direct titrimetric procedure for the determination of sodium and potassium alkyl xanthates has been evolved using potassium periodate as oxidant in natural medium. The end point was determined visually using amylose as indicator. The same method was applied for analyzing carbon-di-sulphide, involving conversion to corresponding xanthate with alcoholic potash. The procedure is accurate to $\pm 1.0\%$, with a relative standard deviation of $\pm 0.5\%$.

CARBON disulphide, as survey of the available literature reveals, may be estimated either by oxidizing it to sulphate and determination of the latter or its conversion to xanthate and its determination. The determination of carbon disulphide as sulfate is gravimetric but gives accurate results with macro amounts only. Volumetric procedures, such as metathesis with barium chromate and iodimetric titration of chromate and the alkalimetric titration of benzidine sulfate², require more technique and time than is ordinarily desirable. Xanthate methods which involve precipitation with a copper salt also suffer from similar disadvantages³⁻⁶. Another complication is imposed by the fact that xanthates, especially the free acids, are quite unstable⁷.

Direct iodimetric determination of xanthates, is most promising owing to its rapidity and precision provided that interference caused by byproducts and decomposition products could be controlled⁷⁻⁹. Time consuming sulfur analysis (Parr bomb) method of xanthate purity is subject to errors introduced by byproducts especially sulphides and disulphides. No attempt has so far been made to determine xanthate purity with potassium periodate,

A new oxidation method for the determination of xanthates has been evolved using neutral solution of potassium periodate since xanthates decompose in presence of acid. Samples are titrated directly with potassium periodate in bicarbonate medium, when xanthates are oxidized to corresponding dioxanthogens:

The procedure when applied to carbon-disulphide, involves conversion to xanthate with alcoholic potassium hydroxide and then determining the xanthate formed with potassium periodate.

Formation of xanthate according to the equation mentioned above is quantitative only when large amount of water is absent,

Experimental

Reagents and Sample: Potassium periodate 0.01M aqueous solution is prepared by stirring the weighed amount of sample for several hours and standardised iodimetrically and by arsenite titration¹⁰.

All xanthate samples were prepared¹¹ by the authors and were recrystallized from the alcohol from which they were synthesized. Carbon disulphide sample used was C. P. Grade. All other chemicals were of reagent grade.

Determination of xanthates: A sample containing 0.1-1.0 m mole of sodium or potassium xanthate, was weighed in a 150-ml Erlenmeyer flask and dissolved in 50-ml of water after which 5 g sodium hydrogen carbonate was added together with 100 mg of potassium iodide and 2 ml 10% starch solution. The contents were titrated with 0.01M potassium periodate solution. The end point was determined by blue colour of starch iodine, formed from the iodide by oxidation with first excess drop of reagent.

Determination of Carbondisulphide: A sample, containing 0.1-1.0 m mole of carbon-di-sulphide was weighed in a small sealed glass bulb and placed in a 150-ml Erlenmeyer flask having 0.5-2.0 ml. of 10% potassium ethoxide and 5 ml of absolute ethanol. The bulb was broken and the sample was released. The contents were swirled for 2 mins. The flask was cooled in an ice-bath then 10 ml of water and 2-3 drops of phenolphthalein indicator were added, it was titrated with molar acetic acid solution until the solution was acid to indicator. 5 g sodium hydrogen carbonate was added and then xanthate formed was titrated with 0.01M potassium periodate as earlier.

The procedure evolved does not require any technical refinement other than those of routine analysis.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 summarises the results for the analysis of carbon-di-sulphide. Quantitative results for the determination of purity of various sodium and potassium alkyl xanthates are recorded in Table 2. The purity determined by potassium periodate, was compared with that found by iodine titration³ and sulfur analysis^{1,2} of the samples. Mercaptans, thiocarbonyl compounds, organic sulphides and sulphocyanide ions, cause severe interferences.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF CARBON DISULPHIDE BY ANALYSIS OF XANTHATE

Taken	Cs ₂ (mg*)	
	Found	Error%
5.78	5.73	-0.5
11.91	12.07	+1.6
24.47	24.25	-0.9
39.21	39.10	-0.3
50.83	51.09	+0.5
65.43	66.11	+1.0

* Average of 10 determinations

TABLE 2—ANALYSIS OF XANTHATE PURITY BY POTASSIUM PERIODATE

Sample	Purity, (%)*		
	Present Method	Iodine titration	Sulfur analysis
K methyl xanthate	96.4	96.8	97.5
K ethyl xanthate	94.8	91.2	89.6
Na ethyl xanthate	89.4	90.2	89.9
K- <i>n</i> -propyl xanthate	99.8	99.9	100.0
Na- <i>n</i> -propyl xanthate	98.5	99.1	99.0
K iso-propyl xanthate	93.7	93.8	94.6
K iso-butyl xanthate	78.5	79.1	78.8
K amyl xanthate	92.3	93.0	92.6
K iso-amyl xanthate	96.7	97.1	97.5
K allyl xanthate	93.6	96.3	96.0
K cyclohexyl xanthate	75.8	79.4	76.2
K sec. butyl xanthate	98.6	99.1	99.6

* Average of 10 determinations

The reaction of carbon disulphide with alcoholic potash is instantaneous and complete, if absolute alcohol is used. The presence of water hampers the reaction but it is not essential to eliminate all traces of water. Freshly prepared alcoholic alkali was used invariably, otherwise erroneous results would be obtained. The conventional treatment of the sample with barium chloride was made in order to circumvent the effect of impurities, contaminated with xanthate samples. The results, obtained by the proposed procedure for the analysis of xanthate and carbon-di-sulphide, are better than those obtained by calculating the purity from total sulfur content.

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